

A Gemination in Some Selected Short Stories: A Contrastive Study

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 23, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: December 30, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Gemination, Sound, Assimilation, Identical, Verse</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6189546</p>	<p>The current study deals with one of the most important topics within linguistics in general and within phonology in particular which is called gemination. This notion denotes a process of consonant re-articulation by which a consonant functions as a syllable coda and belongs to the onset of the following syllable. The problem of the study is that some learners face difficulties within interpretation of the gemination phenomenon. The study also aims at re-visiting the concept of "gemination" and its details in both English and Arabic. It is hypothesized that gemination is usually more employed in Arabic than in English.</p> <p>To perform its aims and confirm its hypothesis, the study adopts the following steps:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> (i) Defining the notion of "gemination". (ii) Stating the structure of gemination. (iii) Following Roach (2009)'s model. (iv) Coming out with a number of conclusions. <p>As for the data analysis, it is limited to analyzing some selected texts of short stories, one for Arabic which is called "ذات الرداء الأخضر" and one for English known as "A Municipal Report". The result is that Arabic is used "gemination" more than English.</p>

Introduction

Crystal (2011: 206) states that "gemination" denotes a concept which is utilized in both phonology and phonetics for a sequence of identical adjacent sounds of a phoneme in particular morpheme, e.g. "Italian notte /notte/ ('night')". By virtue of the syllable divisions, a geminate successive sounds cannot be regarded as merely a "long consonant", and transcriptional differences usually indicate this, "e.g. [-ff] is geminate, [-f:] is long". The special manner of geminates involve a certain concentration in some models to "non-linear phonology", as units of the discussion of the ways in that quantitative phenomenon has to be represented.

He (ibid) assumes that the concerned long sounds that cannot be classified by "epenthetic vowels" are stated to show geminate 'inseparability' or 'integrity'. They fail to subject rules since solely a part of the construction obeys the structural descriptions. True geminate sounds are distinguished with 'apparent' or 'fake' geminates, where similar sounds have been produced adjacent in terms of morphological concatenations. Furthermore, Carr (2008: 62) maintains that gemination is a process whereby non-geminate, a single, consonant undergoes lengthening in order to become a geminate sound. For instance, in Malay language, ifa root terminating in a consonant links with a suffix initiating with a vowel, such consonant represents gemination. Thus, the root "/lɔp/ + suffix /an/" is articulated "[lɔtɔppan]".

For Hayes (1989:254), the following lines are worth mentioning:

"gemination" cannot be interpreted without defining the concept of mora. Mora is "a concept that indicates a minimal unit of metrical time or weight". Mora is also utilized in some approaches of "non – linear phonology" (e.g. prosodic and metrical phonology like an independent tier of phonological representations). The investigation of phonemes to moras is often adopted solely to syllabic coda and nucleus (rhyme), not to "the onset" (rhyme asymmetry/onset).

In conclusion, Katamba (1989: 107) summarizes that "gemination occurs when two identical consonants are adjacent to each other in the same syllable as in English penknife [pen:aɪf]". That is to say, it takes place when a certain segmental production which is extended covering what might be double distinct sounds. Geminate consonants consider the highest degree of the so-called hierarchy.

1.2 Structure of Gemination

Watson (2002:233) explains that the existence of "geminate consonants" within word – final and word – medial position, as in, "broadcast/brɔ:gkɑ:st/". Two contrastive attitudes by which the "geminate consonants" can be represented: the prosodic length investigation of geminates whereby geminate sounds are realized particular consonant phoneme dealt with "two C- slots". The latter one is called moraic weight representations where geminate consonants are realized consonants connected to moras.

In this respect, Delattre(1971:132)views that a geminate sound can be distinguished from along consonant in thata geminate includes two stages in itsproduction. For example, a geminated sound "/b/", involves the following diagram:

He (ibid) illustrates that any geminate consonant has two similar consonants". The first one functions coda and the latterfunctions the onset of a following syllable. Additionally, long consonants are counted as one segment functioning double timing slots:

1.3 Assimilation –Gemination Relation

Carr (2008:16) states that assimilation refers to a phenomenon whereby two, naturally adjacent, segments are more similar to each other. An example of place assimilation of production is found in successive, as in, "ten boys" in English, where the "/n/ of ten"s being assimilated to the place of production of "the following bilabial stop, like, /tembɔɪz/". Besides, Skandera and Burleigh (2011: 91) maintain that "assimilation across word boundaries occurs much more often, for examples: ten pigs [tem pigz], good boy [gubbɔi]"

In this respect, Roach (2009:110) states that is an important difference in normal connected speech indicates the way that segments belonging to a word can lead to changes in segments belonging to identical words. He (ibid) exemplifies the following words: *light blue* /laɪtblu:/ becomes /laɪpblu:/" and "*broadcast* /brɔːdkaːst/ becomes /brɔːgkaːst/.

Additionally, Lorenz (2013: 35) maintains that assimilation refers to a process by which a speech segment is effected by the surrounding sounds making them more identical to the "plural forms of *cats* /kæts/, but *dogs* /dɔgz/", "*ten pence* as /tem pens/", in which /n/ is assimilated in place to following /p/ becoming /tep pens/

1.4 Data Analysis

The present part is concerned with the analysis of data. It is limited to (4) selected texts of the short story "*A Municipal Report*" which is written by Henry (2009). The qualitative method is adopted in the current study. These selected texts will be investigated in relation to gemination depending basically on Roach (2009)'s model.

Text (1)

"The invader was a young man with **light blue** eyes, a hanging lip, and hair the exact colour of the little orphan's (afterward discovered to be the earl's daughter) in one of Mr. Blaney's plays"

Discussion

Concerning the previous text, the two words **light** and **blue** represent the germination process. It can be found that the voiceless plosive sound /t/ being geminated with the adjacent voiced bilabial sound /b/. Thus, the two adjacent words *light blue* /laɪtblu:/ will be articulated as /laɪpblu:/.

Text (2)

"Of course they have, in the climate, an argument that is good for half an hour while you are thinking of your coal **bills** and heavy underwear"

Discussion

It has been noticed that the current text has the word *bills* involving germination. The form *bills* represents assimilation of place where the segment /s/ is produced as /z/ by virtue of the adjacent voiced approximant sound /l/.

Text (3)

"Its upper right-hand corner was **missing**, and it had been torn through in the **middle** but joined again".

Discussion

Two words involving germination can be distinguished in this sample. The first word is *missing* where the two adjacent sounds are represented as a geminated word *missing* /mɪsɪŋ/. Similarly, the second word *middle* /mɪdl/ involved two identical sounds that constitute a geminated sound.

Text (4)

"On the surface," said Azalea Adair. ***I have travelled*** many times around the world in a golden airship wafted on two wings - print and dreams".

Discussion

With reference to the current text, the germination happens within the word boundary *I've travelled* since two segments occur adjacent each other. That is, the sound /v/ has become similar with the following /t/ regarding the intensity of articulation "the manner of articulation", "*I've travelled*" is pronounced as: /aiftrəvəld/.

2. Gemination in Arabic

2.1 Definitions

Muhammad (2001: 75) defines germination as "the pronunciation of the sound twice or giving it more duration". All of segments in Arabic can either be long or short within production, the period of the long sound is the double (geminated) of that of short ones. Such process can be adopted to all vowels and consonants. Besides, Ryding (2005: 688) explicates that germination is "the process of doubling the length or strength of a consonant". Gemination is regarded as both a spelling and pronunciation property indicating that consonants are articulated with double focus or strength, (ibid).

Moreover, Hassan (1983: 119) adds that geminate consonants can be considered as similar clusters. As syllable boundaries are differentiated, the first constituent of the clusters whether identical or non-identical is the coda of the previous syllable, whereas the second one will normally be the initiating of the subsequent syllables, for examples:

- مَثْن = م - ت - ت - ن
- أَبْد = ب - ب - د

He (ibid: 120) maintains that the second segments are denoted and geminated in relation to the diacritic (ُ) which must be employed in terms of writing to affirm that "gemination occurs on this sound and in such a case it is referred to as "mushaddad" i.e., geminated". In Arabic, however, gemination may change the word meanings, as in, the word حمام with germination which denotes pigeons but it points out حمام "bathroom" if it is geminated.

Consequently, a long vowel is considered as a "monophthong" and not a "diphthong". In contrast to the identical strings, they involve the same value in the articulation through the syllables. The long vowel might be regarded as similar to a geminate consonant, like: "/kaatib/ or /ka: tib/ = (كاتب)".

Ryding (2005: 24) maintains that in Arabic, gemination phenomenon is known as "tashdiid" which is utilized to avoid writing down a letter twice. He (ibid) adds that Arabic involve a "diacritical symbol" that is put above doubled consonants. It is made with twice as a matter of emphasis. Such symbol is called as "shadda", (ّ). The same is also adopted to short vowels, "shadda" which does not normally seem in written texts, but it is essentially observing that it is there. Some instances are illustrated this fact:

Table (1) Arabic words having "shadda" (ّ)

Words	Meanings
Freedom	حرية Hurriyya
Pomegranate	رمان Rummaan
to appoint	عين Ayyana
Love	حب Hubb
Doubt	شك Shakk
Surgeon	جراح jarraaH
Very	جدا jidd-an

The gemination phenomenon may result from lexical root including "a doubled root consonant, like, the root h-b-b for hubb, 'love'", or it actually may result from derivational rules, that is, it may alter the meanings of words and their forms. For example, the verb stem "daras" indicates "to study" but a derived form of that verb, "darras", with doubled "arr", indicating 'to teach.' Such senses are interrelated, but not similar, (ibid).

To sum up, Johnstone (1991:44) concludes that geminated sounds may work together with short vowels. It is significant to notice that any letter with "shadda" symbol on it is called as "mushaddad". For instance if one has (ّ) it is indicated geminated or mushaddad. Letters with shadda may carry one of "three short vowels" in Arabic. These vowels can be realized by diacritics under or above a letter. An instance of this is the (ن) letter that can involve two diacritics; one to label gemination and the other is to label the short vowel (نْ , نَ , نِ). Such letters can be investigated in order to reflect that they often have two letters, each of such letters involve its own diacritic as it is shown below:

- نْ + نْ = نّ
- نْ + نَ = نّ
- نْ + نِ = نّ

2.2 Assimilation - Gemination Relation

Ryding (2005: 24) affirms that gemination may also occur by virtue of assimilation process, that is, the absorption of a single sound into another. In this case, the process is not a matter of phonemic but phonetic. That is to say, it refers to a rule of production which does not affect the meaning of a word. For example, "the /l/ of the definite article /al-/ is assimilated to certain consonants when they begin words (e.g., al-daftar, 'the notebook,' is pronounced ad-daftar)".

2.3 Data Analysis

The part is concerned with the analysis of data. It is limited to (4) selected texts of the short story " ذات الرداء الاخضر " which is written by Jadu (2008). The qualitative method is adopted in the current study. These selected texts will be investigated in relation to gemination depended on Ryding (2005: 24)'s model.

Text (1)

"أمرتُ الأمُّ ابنتَهَا الصَّغِيرَةَ أَنْ تَحْمِلَ الْغَدَاءَ وَتَذْهَبَ إِلَى أَبِيهَا فِي الْحَقْلِ؛ لِيَأْكُلَ وَيُوَصِّلَ عَمَلًا."

Translation

"A mother asked her little girl to take the food of lunch to the field for her dad to eat and go on working"

Discussion

It is observed that the preceding text has three words having germination which is used to emphasis or strength. In Arabic, such doubling phenomenon is called "tashdiid". The first word is (الأمُّ) having (م) consisting of (م + م). As for the last one, الصغيرة is the result of assimilation, the absorption of one sound into another. That is, the "definite article /-ال/" is assimilated to (ص) produced as "as-sageera".

Text (2)

"هَمَّتِ الْفَتَاةُ بِالْخُرُوجِ مِنَ الْبَيْتِ وَلَكِنَّمَا عَادَتْ إِلَى أُمِّهَا أُخْرَى وَهِيَ حَزِينَةٌ"

Translation

"The little girl got ready to go out but she came back sadly to her mum".

Discussion

Concerning the current text, three words having gemination. The first word is (هَمَّتِ) having (م + م) which represents semantic root involving "a doubled root consonant", that is, the root ه-م-ت. The second word (لكنها) where the geminate sound is (ن) having (ن + ن) whereas the geminate sound in the third word (أمها) is (م). The last geminate sound is existed within the word (مرة) where the sound (ر) is geminated.

Text (3)

"قَبِلَتِ الْفَتَاةُ الطَّيْبَةَ اعْتِدَارَ الْأُمِّ"

Translation

"The good girl accepted her mum's apology"

Discussion

As far as the current text is concerned, it is observed that there are two words involving gemination. The first two words are الطيبة and الأم. That is to say, the first word الطيبة which represents lexical root involving "a doubled root consonant", that is, the root ط-ي-ب. The second word الأم where the geminate sound is (م)

Text (4)

"وَأَنْطَلَقَتْ إِلَى حَقْلِ أَبِيهَا وَهِيَ سَعِيدَةٌ بِرَدَائِهَا الْأَخْضَرَ الَّذِي يُشْبِهُ إِلَى حَدِّ كَبِيرٍ لَوْنُ الزُّرُوعِ الْمُثْمَرَةِ فِي أَيَّامِ الرَّبِيعِ"

Translation

"And went to her dad's field happy with her green dress that looked like the fruitful plants in the days of spring"

Discussion

Four geminated words can be distinguished in the current text. The first geminated word is الذي where the letter (ل) is geminated. The second word is حد involving (د) which is geminated. The third word is الزروع where the letter (ر) is geminated. Finally, the letter (ي) is geminated in the word أيام.

3. Differences and Similarities

It has been noticed the following crucial points:

1. In Arabic, if gemination occurs across word-boundary it is denoted as "ادغام" which is similar to English as gemination occurs across word boundary within assimilation. For examples:

متن = م - ت - ت - ن /

- ten pigs /tempɪgz/, good boy /gʊbbɔɪ/.
2. Common location of gemination process in English exists medially and finally while in Arabic a geminate sound exists in different word positions.
 3. Gemination in English can be regarded not solely phonological phenomenon but also morphological one, while in Arabic gemination phenomenon is considered as a phonological phenomenon only because it makes contrast in word meaning.
 4. In Arabic writing system, gemination is marked by employing a diacritic put above the geminate consonant known as (shadda), such as, "رَمَانٌ، حَرِيَّةٌ، حَمَامٌ". As opposed, no mark is employed to indicate the occurrence of gemination phenomenon in English.
 5. In Arabic, long vowels are identical to geminate consonants, that is, gemination phenomenon exists even within vowels, like: "/kaatib/ or /ka: tib/ = (كاتب)". In contrast, there are long vowels but they are not counted as geminate vowels.
 6. Arabic utilizes germination process as an essential part of its writing in addition to phonological patterns. In contrast, English reflects it in particular conditions.
 7. Gemination is realized in production by doubling the articulation of the geminate segments in both Arabic and English. For instances:
 - "roommate /'ru:mmet/"
 - "nighttime /'naɪttaɪm/"
 - "حَمَامٌ (حمام)"
 - "حَرِيَّةٌ (حررية)"

Conclusion

The following points are concluded:

1. Concerning English germination, it is a "process whereby a single, non-geminate, consonant undergoes lengthening to become a geminate consonant". The following points are also noticed:
 - A geminate is a string of two identical consonants. The first occupies a syllable coda and the second is reproduced as the onset of a following syllable.
 - Gemination happens if two similar consonants are actually adjacent to each other within the same syllable, such as, the English word "penknife /pen:aɪf/".
 - Assimilation refers to a process in which two (normally adjacent) segments are more similar to each other. An example of place assimilation of articulation is found in successive, like, "ten boys".
2. As for Arabic germination, it refers to "the process of doubling the length or strength of a consonant". The following points are also related:
 - Geminate consonants can be considered as similar clusters.
 - Long vowels are regarded as "monophthong and not diphthong". In contrast to the identical sets, they involve the same importance in the production of the syllables. The long vowels could be counted as identical to geminate consonants, like: "/kaatib/ or /ka: tib/ = (كاتب)".
 - Gemination may also be "the result of assimilation, the absorption of one sound into another".
 - Finally, Arabic, as opposed to English, is frequently utilized germination. In this case, the hypothesis of the study is verified, i.e. germination usually more employed in Arabic than in English.

References

- Carr, P. (2008). *A glossary of phonology*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press
- Crystal, D. (2011). *A dictionary of linguistics and phonetics*, Oxford: Blackwell Publishing Ltd.
- Delattre, P. (1971). *Pharyngeal features in the consonants of Arabic, German, Spanish, French, and American English*. Routledge: Phonetica.
- Hassan, S. (1983). *The phonetics of Arabic: Arabic phonology*. Jeddah: Al Nadi Al Arabi Al Thaqafi.
- Henry, O. (2009). *A municipal report*. London: The Floating Press.
- Hayes, B. (1989). *Compensatory lengthening in moraic phonology*. Routledge: London.
- Katamba, F. (1989). *An introduction to phonology*, Malaysia: Longman.
- Lorenz, F. (2013). *Basics of phonetics and English phonology*. Logos Verlag Berlin GmbH.
- Muhammad, M. (2001). *Arabic phonetics*. Riyadh: Al Tawba Library.
- Roach, P. (2009). *A little encyclopedia of phonetics*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Ryding, K. (2005). *A Reference grammar of modern standard Arabic*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Skandera, P. and Burleigh, P., (2005). *A manual of English phonetics and phonology*, Berlin: Gunter Narr Verlag Tübingen.
- Watson, J. (2002). *The phonology and morphology of Arabic*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

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